

Thermodynamic study of interaction between a cationic surfactant and an anionic azo dye in aqueous solution

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Abstract : The interactions between an anionic azo dye Acid Orange 5 (AO5) and the cationic surfactant cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) have been studied by conductometric and surface tension. The effect of increasing the proportion of dye on the Critical Micelle Concentrations (CMC) of surfactant, as well as the impact of increased temperature, has been investigated to understand the different types of interactions for the formation of a dye-surfactant ion pair. The results revealed that the CMC values have reflected a tendency towards increasing in the values with increasing in the proportion of the azo dye in the surfactant solutions which is unfavorable for micellization. It has been concluded that the relation between temperatures and CMC followed U-shape behavior in dye-surfactant mixture solutions. Significantly, the interactions of dye-surfactant are spontaneous based on the negative values of ΔG^0_{mic} for all systems. However, at low temperatures; the micellization process is endothermic ($\Delta H^0_{mic} > 0$) of dye-surfactant mixture solutions, and become exothermic ($\Delta H^0_{mic} < 0$) at high temperatures. The entropy contribution of micelle formation, ΔS^0_{mic} presents positive values.

Keywords : Azo dye, cationic surfactant, conductivity, micellization, surface tension.

Introduction

The interactions between dye and surfactant are significant in a variety of dyeing processes as well as in chemical research, for example, photosensitization, biochemistry and analytical chemistry¹⁻³. One of the basic parts of data for understanding the process of dyeing and finishing textile materials the nature of these interactions. To study this phenomenon, the researchers referred back to many researches to investigate from the complex formation which resulted from the interactions between dye and surfactant and for the process of the shape and size of the complex⁴⁻⁸. Numerous researches in the interaction between surfactants and dyes has been investigated. However, researches in this part are still significant and exciting to develop the dyeing process from theoretical, economical, technological and environmental points of view. So, studies the interactions between dye and surfactant supply valuable data for industrial applications, likewise, the investigations into the behavior of different dyes in surfactant aqueous solutions can provide useful data for understanding the thermodynamics and kinetics of the

dyeing process and the finishing of textile material. The greatest commonly used measurement techniques for studying this area are conductometry, surface tension, UV-Vis spectroscopy and using surfactant selective electrodes^{9,10}.

Dyes show significant structural variety, and can be classified by their chemical structure or their application to the fiber kind. Dyes must carry one or more functionalities giving the dye color, termed chromophores, as well as an electron withdrawing or donating substituents that cause or intensify the color of the chromophores, named auxochrom. The chromophore group can be a base for dye classification. Azo ($-N=N-$), methine ($-CH=$), nitro ($-NO_2$), carbonyl ($-C=O$) and quinoid groups are the most significant chromophores. The highest significant auxochromes are amine ($-NH_2$), sulfonate ($-SO_3H$), carboxyl ($-COOH$) and hydroxyl ($-OH$) groups. Furthermore, dyes may be classified according to their solubility to soluble dyes like basic, acid, metal complex, direct, mordant and reactive dyes or insoluble dyes including azoic, sulfur, vat and disperse dyes¹¹. Azo dyes, which are aromatic compounds with one or more $-N=N-$ groups,

found the main class of synthetic dyes used in commercial applications. Approximately, 40,000 different dyes and pigments are used industrially probably more than 2,000 different azo dyes are now used and over than 7×10^5 tons of these dyes are produced annually worldwide¹².

The aggregation in a solution is one of the physical characteristics of surfactants. Many physical properties of the surfactant solutions change suddenly; when the aggregation shaped, within a narrow concentration range. Micelle formation of a surfactant in solution is one type of aggregation, and the narrow concentration range is called the critical micelle concentration (CMC), above which micelles are formed in the solutions. Some parameters of micellization, for instance, aggregation number (n), and CMC can differ by changing the surrounding medium. Several factors are affected in micellization, for instance, surfactant nature (hydrophobic volume, head group area and chain length), temperature, solvent, additive, pressure, pH, ionic strength, etc.¹³. Moreover, cationic surfactants offer some further advantages over other types of surfactants. These substances along with their surface activity, show antibacterial properties and are used as cationic softeners, lubricants, retarding agents, anti-static agents and in some cases consumer use¹⁴.

Numerous studies in dye-surfactant interactions in aqueous solutions have been did, mostly in dyeing systems, where level dyeing is controlled by surfactants. When the charge of the surfactant is opposite of that of a dye, the attractive forces between surfactant and dye lead to dye-surfactant complex formation in the solution, resulting in level dyeing. The investigation of cationic surfactant anionic dyes has shown that the importance of long-range electrical forces is basically to bring the dye anion and the surfactant cation close enough to enable the action of short-range non-coulombic attractive van der Waals forces and hydrophobic interactions. So, the long-range electrostatic forces along with short-range attractive forces are responsible for the dye-surfactant ion pair formation¹⁵⁻¹⁹.

The purpose of this paper is to investigate the interactions between the cationic surfactant cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) and an anionic dye Acid Orange 5 (AO5). To confirm these interactions, both conductometric and surface tension methods were imple-

mented. Moreover, to understand the significant of different types of interactions for the formation of a dye-surfactant ion pair, a series of surface tension and conductance measurements were performed at three different temperatures as well as at different proportions of the dye in the surfactant solutions. Moreover, to identify the interaction between dye and surfactant and to determine the thermodynamic functions, the critical micelle concentrations were calculated.

Experimental

Materials :

The cationic surfactant cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB), $(C_{16}H_{33}N(CH_3)_3Br)$, was purchased from Acros Organics® and used as received. The anionic dye C.I. Acid Orange 5 (AO5), sodium 4-[[4-(phenylamino)phenyl]azo]benzenesulfonate, $Na(C_6H_5NHC_6H_4N=NC_6H_4SO_3)$, common name, "Tropaeolin OO", C.I. number (13080) was Sigma chemicals® and used without further purification. Fig. 1 illustrates the chemical structure of dye and surfactant used in this study.

Fig. 1. Molecular structure of (a) Acid Orange 5; (b) cetyltrimethylammonium bromide.

Preparation of solutions :

Doubly distilled water was used for sample preparation and dilution. Stock solutions of surfactant and dye were $1 \times 10^{-2} M$ (364.45 g/mol, 3.6445 g), $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ (375.4 g/mol, 0.3754 g), respectively. In order to obtain accurate value of CMC, above and below the CMC of surfactant solutions were measured. 5, 10% (v/v) of dye-surfactant solutions were prepared. These solutions are placed on a constant temperature water bath before measurements at 298.15, 308.15 and 318.15 K.

Instruments and methods of measurements :

The electrical conductivity was measured with a conductometer; model B36664 from Thermo Scientific®, and the conductivity cell was calibrated with KCl solution in the appropriate concentration range. The cell constant was 0.10 cm⁻¹.

Surface tension measurements were done by applying du Nouy ring method using a Sigma 700 from Attention® model tensiometer and platinum ring.

Water bath Lauda CS-C20 Circulating Bath. Control accuracy is ±0.01 °C.

Results and discussion

Conductivity behavior of dye-surfactant interaction :

Conductivity measurements were performed for pure surfactant and mixture of dye-surfactant at various temperatures in order to evaluate the CMC as shown in Table 1. It is known that the specific conductivity is linearly correlated to the surfactant concentration in both the premicellar and in the postmicellar areas, being the slope in the premicellar region greater than that in the postmicellar region²⁰. The CMC is the intersection point between these two straight lines. In Fig. 2, the specific conductance (κ) (mS cm⁻¹) for pure surfactant CTAB and mixture of (5, 10% AO5-CTAB) is presented as a function of surfactant CTAB concentration at 298.15, 308.15 and 318.15 K.

At constant temperature, Fig. 2 illustrates that the specific conductance values of the dye-surfactant mix-

tures decreased when the proportion of the dye in the surfactant solutions increased. The decrease in the measured values can be explained by the formation of a non-conducting or a less-conducting specie in the solution²¹. This behavior is due to interionic attraction. At low proportion of the dye in the surfactant solutions, the ions are relatively far apart. So, they exert little influence upon one another. As the proportion of the dye in the surfactant solutions is increased, the ions come closer to each other. The attraction between ions results in a decrease of their speeds and consequently in the specific conductance of the solution.

Surface tension behavior of dye-surfactant interaction :

The surface tension (γ) (mN m⁻¹) for pure surfactant and mixture of dye-surfactant is presented as a function of natural logarithm surfactant CTAB concentration at 298.15, 308.15, and 318.15 K in Fig. 3. The surface tension (γ) of surfactant was measured for a range of concentrations above and below the critical micelle concentration. The CMC values were determined at sharp break points in surface tension against the natural logarithm of the concentration curves are given in Table 1.

As can be observed from Fig. 3, the surface tension decreased when the surfactant concentrations increased for the pure surfactant aqueous solutions. This is a common behavior revealed by surfactants in solution and is used to determine their purity and CMCs, since CMC is characteristic phenomena for each pure surfactant²².

Furthermore, the surface tensions of dye-surfactant

Table 1. Thermodynamic parameters for pure CTAB and mixture of % AO5-CTAB, using conductance and surface tension methods

%	T	Conductance technique					Surface tension technique				
		CMC × 10 ³	ΔG^0_{mic}	ΔH^0_{mic}	ΔS^0_{mic}	$T\Delta S^0_{mic}$	CMC × 10 ³	ΔG^0_{mic}	ΔH^0_{mic}	ΔS^0_{mic}	$T\Delta S^0_{mic}$
0	298.15	1.0242	-17.064	-5.170	0.0399	11.89	1.025	-17.062	-5.100	0.040	11.962
	308.15	1.0380	-17.602	-5.530	0.0392	12.08	1.032	-17.617	-5.447	0.039	12.169
	318.15	1.1788	-17.837	-5.890	0.0375	11.95	1.176	-17.843	-5.807	0.038	12.036
5	298.15	1.1560	-16.764	3.180	0.0669	19.94	1.155	-16.766	3.252	0.067	20.018
	308.15	1.1070	-17.437	3.390	0.0676	20.83	1.105	-17.442	3.474	0.068	20.915
	318.15	1.2470	-17.688	-10.01	0.0241	7.67	1.257	-17.667	-10.856	0.021	6.811
10	298.15	1.1902	-16.691	0.370	0.0572	17.06	1.194	-16.684	0.222	0.057	16.905
	308.15	1.1839	-17.265	0.390	0.0573	17.66	1.190	-17.252	0.237	0.057	17.489
	318.15	1.2730	-17.633	-6.140	0.0361	11.49	1.276	-17.627	-5.891	0.037	11.736

Units : T (K); CMC (M); ΔG^0_{mic} , ΔH^0_{mic} (kJ mol⁻¹); ΔS^0_{mic} (kJ mol⁻¹ K⁻¹); $T\Delta S$ (kJ mol⁻¹).

Fig. 2. Specific conductance (κ) (mS cm^{-1}) against concentration (M) for pure CTAB and mixture of (5, 10% AO5-CTAB) at different temperatures (a) 298.15 K, (b) 308.15 K, (c) 318.15 K.

mixtures were decrease than the pure surfactant solutions. The surface tension decreased in the presence of dye at

Fig. 3. Surface tension (γ) (mN m^{-1}) against in concentration (M) for pure CTAB and mixture of (5, 10% AO5-CTAB) at different temperatures (a) 298.15 K, (b) 308.15 K, (c) 318.15 K.

low CTAB concentrations relative to that of the pure CTAB, perhaps as a result of the higher hydrophobicity of the dye-surfactant complexes, which shaped rapidly under ionic and electrostatic interactions. The hydrophobic species performed as a nonionic surfactant and decreased the surface tension relative to the pure CTAB solution because no electrostatic repulsion was present at the surface²³.

The result obtained from the measurements of CMC corresponded with those previously obtained from specific conductance measurements. A valid evidence for such correspondence is that at 318.15 K, the CMC values measured by conductivity for pure surfactant and 5, 10% dye-surfactant were 1.1788, 1.2470, 1.2730, respectively, which are almost comparable of those obtained by surface tension technique $(1.176, 1.257, 1.276) \times 10^{-3} M$, respectively. Likewise, the CMC values (with given percentage at all temperatures) were found to be in agreement with measured specific conductivity as shown in Table 1. Consequently, coincide results of conductometric and surface tension techniques confirmed the interaction between dye and surfactant, and the effect of increasing the proportion of dye.

Temperature dependence of CMC :

As can be observed from Fig. 4, the curves show a typical U-shape cause to the temperature increases, the CMC initially decreases and then increases by using two techniques for dye-surfactant mixture solutions. Two different effects cause this behavior, one of these effects is the hydration of the head group, and the other effect is

Fig. 4. The variation of CMC as a function of temperature for mixture of (5, 10% AO5-CTAB) at different temperatures using conductometry (squares) and surface tension (circles) techniques.

the structured water molecules surrounding the hydrophobic alkyl chain. The increase in temperature produces a decrease in the hydration of the head group and an increase in the breakdown of the structured water molecules surrounding the hydrophobic alkyl chain. The first favors micelle formation while the second does not. At lower temperatures, the first effect is dominant, while at higher temperatures the second effect is dominant; therefore the minimum represents the compensation of both effects. The second effect becomes greater when the hydrophobic chain length increases. The decrease in the minimum, when the hydrophobicity increases, is a confirmation of this effect²⁴⁻²⁸.

Determination of thermodynamic parameters :

The thermodynamic parameters of micellization in aqueous solutions were determining; in order to know more about the process of micellization. The standard Gibbs free energy changes, of micelle formation per mole, ΔG^0_{mic} , can be determined by :

$$\Delta G^0_{mic} = RT \ln CMC \tag{1}$$

whereas R is the gas constant and T is the absolute temperature. The standard enthalpy micelle formation, ΔH^0_{mic} , can be obtained from the temperature variation of CMC by applying the Gibbs-Helmholtz equation to eq. (1) :

$$\Delta H^0_{mic} = -RT^2 d \ln CMC / dT \tag{2}$$

Obviously, the entropy of micelle formation can be determined when the Gibbs free energy and the enthalpy of micelle formation are obtained, by :

$$\Delta S^0_{mic} = (\Delta H^0_{mic} - \Delta G^0_{mic}) / T \tag{3}$$

The interactions of AO5-CTAB were spontaneous based on the negative values of ΔG^0_{mic} for all systems. Moreover, results revealed that the values of Gibbs free energy of micellization become slightly more negative as the temperature increases reflecting that the dehydration of surfactant molecules is predominant factor in the formation of micelles at higher temperature. However, a reverse tendency is observed when increasing of the proportion of the dye in the surfactant solutions demonstrating that the process of micellization became less spontaneous²⁹.

Fig. 5 illustrates the temperature dependence of ΔH^0_{mic} for all mixture compositions system. Obviously, the en-

Fig. 5. The variations of ΔH^0_{mic} (squares) and $T\Delta S^0_{mic}$ (circles) as a function of temperature using (a) conductometry, (b) surface tension techniques.

thalpy of micellization ΔH^0_{mic} is negative and slightly dependent on temperature for pure surfactant³⁰. However, at low temperatures; the micellization process is endothermic ($\Delta H^0_{mic} > 0$) of dye-surfactant mixture solutions and become exothermic ($\Delta H^0_{mic} < 0$) at high temperatures²⁵.

In all temperature range, the entropy contribution of micelle formation ΔS^0_{mic} represents positive values and decreases with increase in temperature. This is owing to the fact, when temperature increase, the head group is more hydrated than the hydrophobic tail which leads to an overall ordering of the system hence, the lowering of the entropy with increase in temperature³¹. The value of $T\Delta S^0_{mic}$ is large and positive; confirming that, in the micellization process, there is a net increase in entropy²⁸.

Conclusions

Critical Micelle Concentration (CMC) of cationic surfactant cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) revealed

tendency for increasing in the values with increasing in the proportion of the dye in the surfactant solutions. Furthermore, the relation between temperatures and CMC followed U-shape behavior in dye-surfactant mixture solutions. Additionally, the CMC values were found to be in agreement with measured specific conductivity and surface tension. The interactions of dye-surfactant are spontaneous based on the negative values of ΔG^0_{mic} for all systems, and become slightly more negative as the temperature increases reflecting that the dehydration of surfactant molecules is predominant factor in the formation of micelles at higher temperature. Significantly, at low temperatures; the micellization process is endothermic ($\Delta H^0_{mic} > 0$) of dye-surfactant mixture solutions, and become exothermic ($\Delta H^0_{mic} < 0$) at high temperatures. The entropy contribution of micelle formation, ΔS^0_{mic} presents positive values.

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